

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING SPECIALISTS TO FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

Umarjonova Nodira Abdukhamid kizi

Trainee teacher of the Department of "Technological Education Methodology" of
Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

E-mail: nodira5655@gmail.com

Artikova Ozoda Burxon qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Faculty of
Professional Education

Student of TT-302 group, "Technological education" field of study

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11242248>

Abstract: this article talks about the process of teaching specialty and specialty subjects to future teachers of technology in higher education institutions, as well as the effectiveness of using interactive methods in teaching.

Key words: Interactive educational technology, educational method, educational goal, teacher, intended result, learner, active method, interactive method.

Introduction.

Currently, there are many directions of pedagogical technology. Today's traditional education consists of the classroom-lesson system, which was formed in the 17th century based on the didactic principles of Y. A. Comensky, and is currently the most widely used in schools around the world. Modern pedagogical technologies were mainly created for the purpose of improving this system in different directions and are currently developing in different directions. They are pedagogical technologies based on improving the pedagogical process, focusing it on the personality of the student; Pedagogical technologies aimed at activating and accelerating students' activities; Pedagogical technologies based on didactic improvement and redevelopment of educational material Pedagogical technologies based on effective management and organization of the educational process; pedagogical technologies adapted to nature; developmental educational technologies and others.

The realization of the goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result in education depends on the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student, as well as the goal they set, the chosen content, method, form, tool, i.e. technology.

It is up to the teacher and the student-student to choose the technology to achieve the goal, because the main goal of both parties is to achieve a specific result, and the technology used by the teacher depends on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group, and the conditions. is selected, for example, it is necessary to work with a computer to achieve the result, maybe a

film, handouts, drawings and posters, various literature, information technology are needed, it depends on the teacher and students [1,2] .

What is an interactive method? While traditional education focuses on the "what, when and where" problems, modern collaborative learning technologies focus on "how to teach?" the problem occupies an important place.

The ratio of the contribution of the teacher and the students in the educational process of teaching the science of technology was different in different periods of human development (civilization). At one time the educators were the leaders, at certain times the learners were the initiators and the positive and negative aspects of such activities have been researched. In the following decades, educational technologies based on the cooperative activity of the teacher and the learner are rapidly developing and becoming popular. Educators call such educational technologies "cooperative pedagogy". Educational technologies based on such cooperation are widely used in developed countries such as the USA, Japan, Great Britain, and Germany, and high efficiency is being achieved. One of these educational technologies is based on interactive teaching methods. The word "Inter" comes from Latin, and in Uzbek it means "intermediate", "middle", "between". Therefore, interactive educational technologies are cooperation based on mutual activity between the teacher and the learner.

Naturally, interactive educational technologies consist of interactive methods (methods) in the educational system. It is based on cooperation in the teaching of technology, and it is designed to increase the activity of students. "interactive" teaching methods aimed at teaching to be able to hide, to sense, feel, control oneself, express one's thoughts clearly and clearly, are developing rapidly. , is having a positive effect. Interactive methods create an atmosphere of competition between small groups in the group, encourage students to be active, and as a result, students learn to cooperate. Any interactive method, when used correctly and appropriately, will teach learners to think independently.

The use of problematic, real-life situations in interactive methods of teaching technology gives very good results. A sad, problematic situation is when a person falls into a difficult situation or situation, which depends on the result of thinking during his activity. In this case, he does not know how to interpret the event or process. Sad, problematic situations strain the mental strength of students, they start looking for ways to clarify the situation. He faces difficulties. A person begins to think only when faced with a problem. He begins to think and perform actions with the knowledge he has, and begins to come to conclusions appropriate to his level. In the teaching of technology, students should be able to tell and explain the

tasks they have completed. They should be able to talk about what they think. It is very important for the teacher to be able to express in his own words the places he did not understand in the process of solving the problem. Methods that teach students to actively work with information are called interactive methods [3,4,5].

In the use of interactive educational technologies in the teaching of technology, students participate as a collective, complementing each other's shortcomings. There are several educational models in pedagogy:

1. Passive, the student plays the role of "object". In this, the student hears and sees.
2. Active, the student participates as a "subject", performs independent work and solves problems.
3. Interactive, in which all students actively participate in the educational process, use games, solve problems together.

There are several types of interactive activities: work in pairs, turn three, carousel, work in small groups, aquarium, unfinished problem, Brownian motion, solving tree, role play, discussion. Interactive educational technology is huge. Each student independently creates new game forms in the class.

Working collaboratively, students ask each other questions and get answers from each other. In the carousel game, students form 2 rings. 1 ring is placed on the outside and the other on the inside. The inner ring is in a seated position. The outer ring is replaced every 30 seconds and should have time to solve the problem.

In the aquarium game, students solve the problem in a circle, and the student at the end evaluates and analyzes the result.

In Brownian motion, all students in the class work together to gather information for the given task.

Technological science opens the doors of opportunities for us to step into new areas of the educational system. Another clear example of this is that the science of labor education has been changed to the science of technology. The main reason for this is that the word "work" has a wide meaning and concept, and it does not correspond to our time of advanced technology and technology. It is necessary to form an infrastructure of innovation by introducing digital technologies and modern methods into the process of technology education. But in order to achieve a high level in this field, first of all, the material and technical base must meet the requirements of the time.

Foydalanilgan rahbariy hujjatlar ro'yxati:

1. S.Kh.Abdullayev, H.M.Akramov, I.T.Uluhanov, A.M.Matkarimov Technology education methodology. Textbook: Namangan-2022.

2. M.M. Akhmetzhanov, U.A. Orinova, Kh.Kh. Saidova, S.Yu. Adizova Methodology of teaching special subjects. Textbook: Bukhara-2022.
3. Z.K.Ismailova, P.M.Makhsudov, O.K.Ergashev, K.J.Matkarimov Methodology of teaching special subjects. Study guide: Tashkent-2019.
4. Azizkhujayeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. ToshDU printing house. Tashkent. 2003
5. N.H. Avliyakov. Modern teaching technology. Tashkent. 2001 66 p.

